

Humanoid Farmer

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Abstract: *Farming is the backbone of the Indian economy and it has been uncharted territory for a technological solution. As of late one of the innovations, Artificial Intelligence has paved the way for digital farming. As an important sector, Indian farming has been facing various challenges like an abrupt change in climatic conditions, spoiling of yields, soil nutrient requirement, pest and weed control, and so forth. Robots with an emerging technique Artificial Intelligence with the integration of various sensors, enhance the better outcome. The network foundation and characteristic simulation of the mobile parameters are set through an Ad-Hoc system or remote sensor-related with each portable robot. Artificial Intelligence with cloud data guarantees and empowers the associated coordinate with mobile robots in all conditions. Through Global Positioning Systems the actual position of the robot is known and the information is retrieved back to the Access point through Beacon message.*

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence; Beacon message; Digital Farming; GPS; Environment monitoring.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is seeing rapid adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) both in terms of agricultural products and in-field farming techniques. Subjective processing, in particular, is all set to become the most convenient technology in agriculture services as it can comprehend, learn, and respond to various circumstances (based on learning) to increase efficiency. Proximity Sensing, moisture sensor, and Image Sensing are the different technologies which are primarily used for wise information combination. One instance of this high-resolution data is Soil Testing. Proximity sensing requires sensors in contact with soil or at a very close range. This aids in soil characterization based on the soil below the surface in a particular place [1]. The wireless network provides the privilege to build a separate multi-hop network and connection between the robot in the field and access point. There is no need for dependence on the settled system as the mobile nodes work under a decentralized and self-computing and arranging networks. While approaching the goal associated with the mobile nodes, it moves around the access point to discover and revert the information collected. The remote mobile node can be deployed anywhere and shaped on the network area in an unconstrained and quick way. Ad-hoc networks [2] are also called a multi-hop network for the favorable position

assigning of the mobile node. Impromptu systems is an investigative way to locate a helpful and correct scientific portrayal for displaying in a few applications, for example, specially appointed correspondence between mobile PCs for conferencing and home systems administration, remote sensor systems, multi-bounce expansions of cell media transmission frameworks, and systems of vehicles. Availability is an essential and extremely basic property of a remote multi-hop network. Remote systems with settled foundation (e.g., cell media transmission systems or remote LANs), it is adequate that every portable hub has a remote connection to no less than one base station. Images of various yields under white light are captured to determine how crops are grown and evolved. Farmers can create various degrees of preparation depends on the yield (crop/fruit) category and include them into discrete stacks before sending them to the market. Remote sensing techniques alongside spectral imaging processing are fundamental to build crop metrics across thousands of acres. It has the potential to acquire a progressive change in terms of how farmlands are monitored by farmers both from time and effort perspective. The robot with knowledge of Artificial Intelligence in agriculture, have a lot of importance as far as overseeing unfavorable climate conditions, profitability gains, exactness cultivating, and yield the executives. Yield Monitoring and Health evaluation of a harvest or plant stays considerably the most noteworthy zones in farming to furnish Robotic solutions in collaboration with Artificial Intelligence [3]. The image capturing and processing in Robots gather precision field images that can be passed through a convolution neural network to identify areas with which yields need water, growth, condition, and requirement in the mid-development stage. As far as tainted plants, by examining crops in both RGB and close infrared light it is conceivable to produce multispectral pictures utilizing devices that have the skill set to identify and notify. The expression "Perfect Place, Right Time, Right Product" summarizes exactness cultivating. This is a progressively precise and controlled procedure that replaces the dreary and labor-intensive part of farming. It likewise gives direction about yield turn, ideal planting and reaping time, water the executives, supplement the executives, pest attacks, and so on. Artificial skillset models trained on plant images can be used to recognize developments in plants. India is partitioned into six significant soil types. In this study, we have tried to make a comprehensive robot that can provide us with on-farm testing of soil, suitable yields to be grown

